

Using Integral Measurements from an Advanced Reactor Demonstration to Update Nuclear Data for Predictive Neutron Transport Simulations

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803934

ABSTRACT

The clean energy transition necessitates significant additions to nuclear capacity, motivating the development of advanced reactor technologies such as the Kairos Power Fluoride-salt-cooled, High-temperature Reactor (KP-FHR). To enhance the accuracy of neutronic simulations and reduce uncertainty in design and safety analyses, this work presents a methodology to update nuclear data through the coupling of the Serpent Monte Carlo code and the SCALE module TSURFER, applied to the generic FHR (gFHR) benchmark. The process demonstrates how integral measurements—specifically, critical fuel height and critical control rod insertion—can be used within a Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) framework to produce statistically consistent adjustments to nuclear data. A simulated measurement using the JEFF 3.3 library serves as a surrogate for physical data, while ENDF/B-VII.1 provides the reference basis for the update.

The workflow includes generating group-wise sensitivity data in Serpent, converting these sensitivities into TSURFER-compatible format, and applying the resulting nuclear data perturbations using the ACE toolkit (ACEtk). The output is a set of updated nuclear data tables that reflect integral experimental behavior, showing improved consistency between simulation and measurement. This fully-simulated demonstration establishes a foundation for utilizing experimental data from the Hermes demonstration reactor and can be expanded to include additional measurements beyond those discussed here. Ultimately, this framework supports the reduction of uncertainty in neutronic predictions, enabling the refinement of safety margins and improved operational efficiency in advanced reactor systems—key steps toward achieving reliable, cost-effective deployment of clean nuclear energy technologies.

Keywords: Nuclear Data, Serpent, Bayesian Update, gFHR simulation, ACE table

1. INTRODUCTION

The clean energy transition is expected to require the addition of hundreds of gigawatts of nuclear capacity in the United States. Kairos Power is developing pebble-bed Fluoride-salt-cooled, High-temperature Reactors (KP-FHRs) for technology demonstration and commercial power generation. This work demonstrates the first step in establishing a method to update nuclear data for KP-FHRs by coupling together Serpent [1] and the SCALE [2] module TSURFER [3] using the gFHR benchmark [4].

Advanced reactors benefit from inherent safety features, but design and licensing of the first advanced reactor deployments require additional safety margin to account for the uncertainties of first-of-a-kind (FOAK) technology. Subsequent deployments of advanced reactors can learn from the measurements and operating history of first iterations to reduce margins and improve operational efficiencies (e.g. reactor power level, fuel utilization, materials limits, cost savings). Measurements in FOAK reactors present a valuable opportunity for adjustment of nuclear data libraries to more accurately model those reactor configurations. Use of adjusted nuclear data is common in commercial reactor fleets in order to improve prediction accuracy for core neutronics analysis, thereby reducing uncertainty and improving

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operational margins. Nuclear data adjustment has been demonstrated for many applications using varying methods. For advanced reactor applications which are represented by relatively few existing benchmarks, including KP-FHR, the accuracy of neutronics predictions may be improved significantly by applying nuclear data adjustment based on measurements from reactor operations.

The later use of this work will be a quantitative study gauging the validity of the method through a simulated experiment performed using the gFHR benchmark [4] - a published computational model of the FHR - so that it can later be applied in a like manner to a physical measurement taken from the Hermes demonstration reactor. In addition, this framework will allow for further development to accommodate the long term goals of this project, which include optimizing the type and locations of flux wires in the Hermes reactor such that the information they can provide is maximized, and the experimental data gained from them can further improve the updated nuclear data library for all subsequent calculations. The demonstration of increased confidence in neutronic simulation in a physical system, such as Hermes, is a pathway to cut down large margins that are in place to satisfy regulatory requirements without sacrificing safety while reducing both quantitative and financial burden.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Description of gFHR and Use of Separate Libraries

The Kairos Power FHR (Fluoride salt-cooled High-temperature Reactor) is a pebble bed advanced reactor that uses FLiBe as the coolant, where pebbles are constructed to be buoyant in the FLiBe such that they rise up through the fueled region of the vessel, with moderation provided by graphite within the fuel pebbles, in separate graphite moderator pebbles, and in a graphite reflector surrounding the core. The first iteration of this FOAK technology will be the Hermes demonstration reactor, a low-power, smaller version of KP-FHR to serve as an avenue to gain experimental data.

A computational benchmark model for the FHR technology has been created, referred to as the generic FHR or gFHR [4]. This will be the model serving as the computational basis of the update system, as well as the mechanism from which the simulated experiment is taken, and later the physical experiment taken from Hermes. However, an update cannot be performed between two identical systems, so the simulated process will involve models using two different nuclear data libraries: the base cross-sections to be updated from ENDF/B-VII.1 [5] and the cross-sections to use in taking the measurement from JEFF [6]. ENDF/B-VII.1 is the preferred library for Serpent transport calculations since it was used in the gFHR benchmark. JEFF 3.3 was selected because it produced noticeably different predictions than ENDF/B-VII.1, enabling a clear demonstration of the update. The transport calculations performed with JEFF 3.3 serve as the surrogate for a physical measurement.

2.2. Documented Industry Update Practices

Previous efforts to adjust nuclear data have relied on comparisons between the integral parameters calculated and measured from well-characterized experiments [7]. There is a heavy presence of light-water reactor benchmarks, where differences between predicted and measured criticality or reaction rate ratios were used to infer systematic biases in the underlying nuclear data. Methods such as Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) adjustment were then applied to update evaluated cross sections and covariance data in a statistically consistent manner. The process often involved the use of large benchmark databases, such as the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICS-BEP) [8], to ensure that the adjustments improved performance on the particular application for which they were applied. These tuned data sets represent a realization of a general purpose library for a specific technology and are used in reactor design and safety analysis.

3. METHODOLOGY

This methodology serves as a framework to update a nuclear data library based on the results of integral measurements. The process for this method revolves around a simulated measurement of the gFHR, which in this work are configuration measurements taken when the gFHR is critical. These results, along with transport-calculated k-eigenvalue sensitivities to nuclear data, are placed into the update code TSURFER [3] in SCALE 6.3.2 to calculate recommended perturbations to the nuclear data so that transport calculations more closely reflect the measurement. The simulated measurement is performed in Serpent using the JEFF 3.3 library, while ENDF/B-VII.1 is the basis for the transport k-eigenvalue and the Serpent-calculated sensitivities to the k-eigenvalue.

3.1. Description of gFHR Experiments

The basis of this work will focus on a fully-simulated demonstration of the proposed methodology to update nuclear data on the gFHR, with the future goal of applying this demonstration to a real-world measurement from Hermes. The primary measurements of this work will be critical dimension measurements, namely critical fuel height and critical control rod insertion.

For the critical fuel height experiment, a 1/M experiment will be done in Hermes to reach first criticality. To achieve this, the core will first be filled with unfueled, moderator pebbles made of graphite, with control and shutdown rods placed where they have low impact in reactivity for the first fuel added. This first fueling will be a mixture of high-assay, low-enriched uranium (HALEU) pebbles, simply referred to as enriched pebbles, and natural (unenriched) uranium. A large group of these mixed pebbles, approximately 20% of the critical mass, will be inserted while the reaction rates are measured with detectors, and the rods will subsequently be backed off to where they have little impact on the next group of pebbles. Another 20% of the critical mass worth of pebbles are then added with the same rod-backing procedure. The detector responses are then used to determine the next amount of pebbles to add, and this process is repeated until first criticality is reached. The level of the fuel at this point is the critical fuel height, and this configuration of the core is referred to as the Alpha core. This procedure is documented and more accurately described by Satvat et al [9] and is visually represented in Figure 1.a.

The critical control insertion measurement will be a similar measurement in a slightly different core arrangement. Starting with the Alpha core in a shutdown state where the control rods are fully inserted, fuel in the same enriched to natural uranium pebble ratio is added until the core region is fully fueled, and this arrangement is called the Lambda core, shown in Figure 1.b. The 1/M experiment is repeated by withdrawing the control rods in increments, such that an examination of the detector responses can inform the next iteration of withdrawal. Once criticality is reached in this configuration, the level of the control rods is the critical control insertion. Each of these core arrangements will be laid out as described in the measurements when modeled, using the gFHR benchmark [4], so that the critical configuration from each can be delineated as the calculated value.

3.2. Process of Updating Nuclear Data

The mathematical method used in the update of nuclear data is the Generalized Linear Least Squares [10] method. This is a common form of a Bayesian update, which uses statistics to leverage new information gained by a measurement. Essentially, GLLS uses the sensitivities of inputs into a problem to adjust those inputs to minimize the difference between measured and calculated values while remaining consistent with the prior input uncertainties.

The code TSURFER [3] is a commonly-used tool for this type of update that is found in the SCALE [2] suite of codes. TSURFER is used to find the solutions to the GLLS equations and returns them in the form of cross-section perturbations to apply to the initial cross-section set. This code requires sensitivities of some response with respect to the nuclear data, the measured value of the response

Figure 1. Startup configurations of the Hermes reactor used to define the integral measurements. (a) The Alpha core configuration at first criticality, where the fuel height defines the critical fuel height measurement. (b) The Lambda core configuration with a fully fueled core and inserted control rods, used to determine the critical control rod insertion (adapted from [9] with permission).

and its uncertainty, and the starting calculated value to perform the GLLS calculation. The response of choice for the experiments discussed will be the k -eigenvalue response, and the sensitivities will be of the k -eigenvalue with respect to the nuclear data. The actual measurement taken in Hermes, however, will not be the k -eigenvalue, but the fuel height at which it becomes critical. The k -eigenvalue here is 1 with uncertainty propagated from the measurement value through the sandwich rule using derivatives calculated with transport using a finite difference. This conversion of measurement to the k -eigenvalue is necessary because the k -eigenvalue is a valid response type in TSURFER and the measurement height is not. TSURFER requires the sensitivities in a specific format that is explicitly printed out by the SCALE sensitivity calculator, TSUNAMI[11]. However, Serpent is the code used to perform the transport, and thus Serpent sensitivities must be used for consistency. This necessitated the development of a script to take the Serpent sensitivity outputs and convert them to the format required for TSURFER.

The output of TSURFER is a list of group-wise cross-section perturbations that represent the solutions to the GLLS equations. These perturbations are limited by TSURFER such that applying them to the cross-sections will not put them out of their uncertainty bounds. The source of covariance data is the default 56groupcov7.1 SCALE covariance library. All nuclide-reaction channels present within the model are considered, but TSURFER will filter out those that fail to meet a minimum relative sensitivity value of 0.001. Thus, not all nuclide-reaction channels are included in the update, only those with a significant impact. For this demonstration, these group-wise perturbations are performed over the SCALE 56-group energy structure. The nuclear data elements of $\bar{\nu}$ (nubar) and χ (fission spectrum) are not included in the current update methodology, but they are planned as future additions to improve the update efficacy. The perturbations in each group are relatively small compared to the magnitude of the cross-section, so group-to-group discontinuities are small enough to approximate continuity.

3.3. Using Updated Nuclear Data in Transport

The nuclear data used by Serpent for neutron transport are in the form of A Compact ENDF, or ACE, table that contains all the continuous energy cross-section data for a specific nuclide at a specific temperature. The recommended changes from TSURFER identify which ACE tables are to be updated, which

are then copied from the default nuclear data library. The group-wise cross-section changes are then performed to each applicable ACE table using the ACE toolkit (ACEtk) [12]. This is a tool developed specifically for the purpose of perturbing data in ACE tables, with relative perturbations specified by reaction and energy range, directly allowing for specified changes over the selected group structure.

The ACEtk will use the TSURFER recommended changes to produce each updated nuclear data file, which Serpent will use directly in transport. Changes performed to each reaction for a single nuclide are summed by group so that the total change can be applied to the total and absorption cross-section tables. Since these perturbations are done over a continuous energy range and they are not all the same, there will be discontinuities at the group boundaries. This ability of using integral measurements to bring neutronic simulation closer to reality will be demonstrated below.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. k-eigenvalue Measurement in Alpha Core

Since TSURFER provides cross-section update recommendations with respect to some transport response, the k-eigenvalue from Serpent is used in the Alpha core experiment as the response to take a measurement from the JEFF 3.3 library and update the ENDF/B-VII.1. The starting k-eigenvalue of the unaltered ENDF/B-VII.1 data for the Alpha core configuration was 1.00569 ± 0.00009 , and the measurement of the JEFF 3.3 k-eigenvalue yielded a value of 1.01398 ± 0.00009 . In the real world experiment, the critical fuel height will have inherent experimental uncertainty, which can be propagated to the k-eigenvalue and given to TSURFER, but since that is not available without the physical measurement, the experimental error of the k-eigenvalue will be taken as 0.1% as an estimate. When the measurement and update framework were used to provide updated cross-sections, those cross-sections were used in Serpent to generate the updated k-eigenvalue, which was 1.01383 ± 0.00009 . This result shows the k-eigenvalue moves in the correct direction towards the measurement and falls within two standard deviations.

4.2. Ranking Influence of Nuclides on Update

To inspect the amount in which the nuclide-reaction channels contribute to the update, the Δk value for each was calculated using a dot product of the TSURFER recommended changes and the k-eigenvalue sensitivities for each reaction channel. Most of these resulted in less than a 1 pcm difference to the update in the Alpha core k-eigenvalue, and these have been filtered out of the results to show only reaction channels with a more significant contribution. Table I gives the result of the individual reaction channel inspection.

The largest contribution to the update comes from the ${}^7\text{Li}(n, \gamma)$ reaction, with the (n, γ) reaction making up the majority of the channels providing a significant update. This is consistent with previous findings that ${}^7\text{Li}(n, \gamma)$ uncertainty is the dominating contributor to k-effective uncertainty for the PB-FHR-Mk1 [13]. This reaction channel receives preference from TSURFER in the update due to its high covariance. It is important to note that JEFF 3.3 and ENDF/B-VII.1 originate with very similar cross-sections for ${}^7\text{Li}(n, \gamma)$, showing that the update does not necessarily align individual cross-sections between the two libraries. The update does, however, provide a set tuned to improve the prediction in simulation. Later work will seek to add measurements to the methodology and inspect cross-sections with high covariance to influence the update to move cross-sections in the correct direction. This practice of ranking individual updates can be expanded to include those additional measurements to perform a comparison that identifies which measurement can provide the best update for a desired reaction channel.

Table I. Contributions of individual nuclide–reaction channels to the Alpha core k -eigenvalue update, expressed as the change in k (pcm) resulting from the TSURFER-recommended perturbations. Values are computed from the dot product of sensitivities and applied cross-section changes and are filtered to include only channels with non-negligible impact.

Nuclide	Reaction	Δk (pcm)
^7Li	(n, γ)	725
^{235}U	fission	21
^{235}U	(n, γ)	20
^{238}U	(n, γ)	19
^{19}F	(n, γ)	14
C	(n, γ)	12
C	elastic	4
^{19}F	elastic	3
^{238}U	elastic	2
^7Li	elastic	1
^9Be	(n, γ)	1

4.3. Inspection of Important Cross-Section Changes to Ensure Proper Update

To check that the perturbation of the ACE tables is representative of the suggested amounts from TSURFER, the group-wise recommended changes of the $^7\text{Li}(n, \gamma)$ and ^{235}U fission cross-sections from TSURFER were plotted, as well as the difference between the unaltered ENDF/B-VII.1 point-wise cross-section data and the updated ENDF/B-VII.1 point-wise cross-section data. These were obtained directly from their ACE tables. The differences for $^7\text{Li}(n, \gamma)$ are plotted in Figure 2.a, and the differences for ^{235}U fission are shown in Figure 2.b. Agreement between TSURFER and the actual cross-section difference is consistent throughout the energy group structure for both reaction channels.

Figure 2. Comparison of TSURFER-recommended group-wise perturbations and the actual differences calculated between the starting and updated ACE tables. Agreement between the prescribed perturbations and the implemented ACE modifications confirms that the update procedure correctly applies the TSURFER adjustments across the 56-group energy structure.

4.4. Testing Update on Lambda Core Inference Calculation

Calculating the critical control insertion was done by calculating the k -eigenvalue over a range of control insertion levels using Serpent and then interpolating between two k -eigenvalues found to be on either side of criticality. The k -eigenvalue result for each library is shown over a range of control in-

sertions in Figure 3. For the starting calculation using ENDF/B-VII.1, the banked control rod height in the Lambda core was found to be 105.3 cm. The monte carlo numerical error for this and the following critical rod height calculations is within 1 cm. The calculated result using the JEFF 3.3 library was 153.2 cm. After the update procedure was performed using the measurement of the Alpha core k-eigenvalue, the updated ENDF/B-VII.1 data yielded a banked control rod height of 150.3 cm. Since the uncertainty of the posterior nuclear data is highly dependent on the measurement uncertainty, and the measurement uncertainty was given an arbitrary value of 0.1%, there is little meaning to the posterior nuclear data uncertainty and thus not reported. From these numbers, the inference calculation achieves a value much closer to the JEFF 3.3, showing the updated library has an improved prediction. It is important to note that this improvement comes without a measurement of the Lambda core incorporated into the update, and the information gained from the Alpha core measurement is valuable to the different core arrangement in Lambda core.

Figure 3. k -eigenvalue as a function of control rod insertion in the Lambda core for ENDF/B-VII.1, JEFF 3.3, and the updated library. The intersection with $k = 1$ defines the inferred critical control rod height. The updated library shifts the prediction toward the surrogate measurement (JEFF 3.3), demonstrating improved predictive capability using information obtained only from the Alpha core measurement.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates a framework for updating nuclear data through the use of integral measurements, leveraging the coupled capabilities of Serpent, the TSURFER adjustment code, and the ACEtk perturbation tool. By applying the methodology to the gFHR benchmark and using JEFF 3.3 transport results as a surrogate measurement, we established a controlled environment in which the performance and internal consistency of the update process could be evaluated prior to application to physical data from the Hermes reactor. The results show the ability to update the nuclear data used by Serpent in ACE tables to reflect the updates provided from TSURFER, and, therefore, perform transport calculations with information gained by an integral experiment.

Parameters of $\bar{\nu}$, fission spectrum, and angular distribution are candidates to expand the update and be investigated in the future. Eventually, the use of this method will transition from simulated to experimental measurements, where physical data from Hermes will offer opportunities to constrain nuclear data for FHR systems. Ultimately, the approach outlined here provides a foundation for increasing the reliability of predictive neutron transport simulations. As additional measurements are incorporated and the methodology is expanded to more diverse responses, the resulting improvements in nuclear data will support optimized designs, reduced licensing margins, and more efficient deployment of FHRs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The first author would like to thank Kairos Power for their funding of and involvement in this work.

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